

Construction of the Meaning of the Song Imagine Jhon Lennon's as a Media for Social Criticism Communication for John Lennon Fans

Astri Dwi Andriani¹, Dera Maharani Sadikin²
Putra Indonesia University

Corresponding Author: Astri Dwi Andriani astridwiandriani@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research is entitled "Construction of Song Meaning Imagine John Lennon's work as a Social Criticism Communication Media for John Lennon Fans at Putra Indonesia University, Cianjur". The objectives of this research include how to construct the meaning of songs Imagine John Lennon's work in the semiotics of Roland Barthes and how social criticism forms in songs Imagine. The theory used in this research is Roland Barthes' semiotic theory. This research uses qualitative research methods with a semiotic approach. The data collection methods used in this research include observation, interviews, documentation, literature study, online data, and data triangulation. The results of this research show that from a denotative level analysis, songs Imagine tells the story of John Lennon's anxiety about what happened in the world in 1971 when the conflict between Vietnam and America occurred. Then, in the connotative level analysis, songs Imagine are John Lennon's dreams for the world and wrap his idealism into the song. In the analysis at the myth level, there is an ideology that is very often mentioned by John Lennon, namely "peace". John Lennon imagined several things in these lyrics which aimed to achieve a life full of peace without conflict.

INTRODUCTION

Harold D. Lasswell in Aan Widodo (2016:37) states that communication is basically a process that explains who, says what, and uses what channels, to whom, with what consequences, or what kind of results. (*Who? Say What? In Which Channel? To Whom? With What Effect?*). That way communication can be done anywhere and anytime and through anything. Including through a song. Songs are a series of notes accompanied by poetry or lyrics. Songs are often used as a medium to convey a message to other people. The lyrics of the song are the message that the communicator wants to convey to the communicant. A poem or lyric is an example of verbal communication. The poetry or lyrics in a song are written by a musician. The lyrics of a song certainly have a meaning or purpose that the writer wants to convey to the audience.

Songs, sometimes carry a big mission for society. Because songs not only provide entertainment but also provide social awareness and social criticism (M. Dwi Marianto and Sunarto in Alfian Yanuar Laksono, 2018:2). John Winston Lennon was born October 9, 1940. Born to Julia Stanley and Alfred Lennon. John's father Alfred (John Lennon) was a sailor who traveled frequently and rarely returned to Liverpool. Even when John was born, Alfred was not present by Julia's side (Hendi Triono, 2010:7-8).

John Lennon is a former member of the Liverpool band The Beatles. Even though he achieved success and popularity with The Beatles, Lennon finally decided to leave the band he pioneered and founded in 1970 (Hendi Triono, 2010:64). Apart from remaining productive as a musical artist, Lennon was also actively involved in the movement against government policies towards war. Lennon campaigned for the anti-war movement, when the Vietnam war was raging in 1969. Lennon and Yoko Ono released a peace song entitled *Give Peace A Chance* (Hendi Triono, 2010:69-70).

As in the title song *Imagine* John Lennon's work which was released in 1971. In this song John Lennon conveys messages that contain social criticism. In the book entitled *Imagine* John Lennon by Hendi Triono, it is written that this song became the theme song for the movement against war policies (Hendi Triono, 2010:69-70). "If one person dreams, then it remains a dream. "But if two people have the same dream, that's reality," said John. John's dream and also most people's dreams at that time were the same, namely *Love Peace No War* (Hendi Triono, 2010:70).

Imagine was Lennon's most successful solo album in terms of sales (Hendi Triono, 2010:72). Album *Imagine* in 1971, became the theme song for the anti-war movement which wanted a peaceful world life. Visuals in the song video clip *Imagine*, the visual appearance is all white, namely wearing white clothes, a white piano, and an all-white room (Hendi Triono, 2010:69).

Unique, song *Imagine* there are still many people who hear it and sing it. This is proven by one of the uploads from the Youtube account 'UNICEF USA', they uploaded a video entitled 'UNICEF #IMAGINE – A Better World for Children' which is where the song is *Imagine* sung by several famous singers

such as Katy Perry, Adam Lambert, Danny O'Donoghue (vocalist of the band The Script), and other famous singers.

In the caption on the video they wrote that, four decades ago, the song *Imagine* John Lennon's work inspired them to look beyond their differences and dream of a more just and peaceful world. With deadly conflict and other dangers threatening children's lives like never before, they also say we need that perspective today more than ever.

For this reason, this research will examine how the meaning of songs is constructed *Imagine* John Lennon's work using Roland Barthes' semiotics and how social criticism can be found in songs *Imagine*. So the researchers found the title, namely 'Song Meaning Construction *Imagine* John Lennon's Work as a Communication Media for Social Criticism for John Lennon Fans at Putra Indonesia University, Cianjur' is the title of this research.

The formulation of the problem in this research is, "How to construct the meaning of songs *Imagine* John Lennon's work as a medium for communicating social criticism for John Lennon fans at Putra Indonesia University, Cianjur?". The purpose of this research is to find out how the meaning of songs is constructed *Imagine* John Lennon's work as a medium for communicating social criticism for John Lennon fans at Putra Indonesia University, Cianjur. As material for preparing a thesis as a final assignment in pursuing a bachelor's degree in Communication Sciences, Putra Indonesia University.

This research has two research objectives. First, to find out how the meaning of the song is constructed *Imagine* John Lennon's work semiotically. Second, to find out what form of social criticism exists in songs *Imagine* by John Lennon. This research is supported by previous research, including, "Music as a Media for Social Criticism (Semiotic Analysis of the Lyrics of the Song "Biru" on the Synesthesia Album Karya Efek Rumah Kaca)" by Hilfani Shaliha (2017), "The Concept of Peace in Songs *Imagine* John Lennon's Works (Semiotic Analysis of Ferninand de Saussure)" by Alfian Yanuar Laksono (2018), "Social Criticism of Song Lyrics (Hermeneutical Analysis of Song Lyrics of the Seringai Music Group, Greenhouse Effect and Homicide)" by M. Khairil Anwar (2017), "Depicting the Social Inequalities of the Belitung Community in the Film Laskar Pelangi" by Muhammad Hanafi (2014).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Semiotika Roland Barthes

Roland Barthes is a leading structuralist figure and is also one of the main developers of Saussure's concept of semiology. Starting from Saussure's principles, Barthes uses syntagmatic and paradigmatic concepts to explain cultural phenomena, such as clothing systems, diets, architecture, paintings, films, advertisements and literary works. He views all of this as a language that has a system of relations and opposition. There are several creations from Barthes which are his legacy to the intellectual world, namely the concept of connotation which is a semiotic key in analyzing culture, and the concept of

myth which is the result of applying connotation in various fields in everyday life. Semiotics as a branch of science shows influence in the fields of fine arts, dance, film art, product design, architecture, including visual communication design.

Tinarbuko in Aldino Agusta Walad (2013:6) also continues that, when viewed from a semiotic point of view, visual communication design is a special "semiotic system", with a vocabulary of signs (*vocabulary*) and syntax (*syntagm*) which is distinctive, which is different from the semiotic system of art. In semantics, visual communication cannot be separated from the communication function. Namely the function of signs in conveying messages (*message*) from a message delivery (*sender*) to the recipients (*receiver*) signs based on certain codes. Even though its main function is communication, it has a significant function (*signification*) namely the function of conveying a concept, content, or meaning.

Continuing Hjelmslev's studies, Barthes created a map of how signs work (Cobley & Jansz in Alex Sobur (2016:69): Cobley and Jansz in Alex Sobur (2016:69) say that, from Barthes' map above, it can be seen that the denotative sign consists of a marker and a sign. However, at the same time, denotative signs are also connotative markers. This is a material element: only if you know the sign "lion" can connotations such as dignity, ferocity and courage become possible.

Denotative

Danesi (2010:274) explains that denotational meaning is the main initial meaning of a sign, text, and so on.

Connotative

Roland Barthes in Sobur (2013:69) explains that connotative signs do not just have additional meaning, but contain both parts of the denotative sign which examine the sign linguistically so that it becomes the basis for its existence. Connotations are cultural meanings that emerge or can be called meanings that arise due to cultural construction. So there is a shift but it remains attached to the symbols and signs (Kriyantono, 2007:268).

Myths

Barthes said that myth is language. So myth is a communication system and myth is a message. According to his description, he argued that myth in this special sense is a development of connotation. The connotation that has been established for a long time in society is myth. Barthes also revealed that myth is a semiological system, namely a system of signs that humans interpret (Hoed in Vera, 2014: 28).

METHODOLOGY

In this research, researchers used a qualitative research methodology with a semiotic approach. The data collection methods used in this research include observation, interviews, documentation, literature study, online data, and data triangulation. Meanwhile, data analysis methods include data reduction, data collection, data presentation, and drawing conclusions or verification.

Apart from that, the researcher chose Roland Barthes' Semiotics theory for this research. Because this theory is very suitable to be used in this research. For data sources, the data sources used include primary and secondary data sources. The primary data sources in this research are the results of interviews and observations obtained in the field. Meanwhile, secondary data sources in this research are in the form of documents or archives, literature studies, and *dataonline*.

There are research objects and subjects in this research. The research object in this study is the construction of song meaning *Imagine* John Lennon's work as a medium for communicating social criticism. Meanwhile, the research subjects in this study were John Lennon fans who were students at Putra Indonesia University, Cianjur with one representative in each faculty.

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. *John Lennon Profile*

John Winston Lennon was born October 9, 1940. Born to Julia Stanley and Alfred Lennon. John's father Alfred (John Lennon) was a sailor who traveled frequently and rarely returned to Liverpool. Even when John was born, Alfred was not present by Julia's side (Hendi Triono, 2010:7-8). He is a former member of the Liverpool band The Beatles. Even though he achieved success and popularity with The Beatles, Lennon finally decided to leave the band he founded in 1970 (Hendi Triono, 2010:64). Before deciding to leave The Beatles, John Lennon made a controversial statement towards society at that time, as in Florentia Senojati (2020:53), when interviewed by the London Evening Standard, he stated "*more popular than Jesus*".

Before The Beatles officially disbanded in 1970, Lennon had already started his career with the Plastic Ono Band, which he formed so he only had to continue the band he had started, after not being in the Beatles, Hendi Triono (2010:65). Apart from remaining productive as a musical artist, Lennon was also actively involved in the movement against government policies towards war. Lennon campaigned for the anti-war movement, when the Vietnam war was raging in 1969. Lennon and Yoko Ono released a peace song entitled *Give Peace A Chance* (Hendi Triono, 2010:69-70).

On December 8 1980 John Lennon died because he was shot by a fanatical fan named David Mark Champman in front of the Dakota apartment where John Lennon and his wife Yoko Ono lived in the United States, (Hendi Triono, 2010:108). Lennon's death is still remembered as a day of mourning for the world of music, as a person who helped shape history *Rock and Roll* world,

including the leader of the peace movement, as well as a generational icon *baby boomer*, Lennon's sudden death was considered the end of a musical era. Moreover, with the fact that we all already know, Lennon was shot dead by someone who claimed to be his own fan (Florentia Senojati, 2020:106). Until now, he is known as one of the musicians with the strongest determination to fight violence and war. During his life, he has composed many songs to convey his message of peace to more people (Florentia Senojati, 2020:95).

B. The Song of Imagine

In Florentia Senojati (2020:99-100) explains that, songs *Imagine* Released in 1971, critics once called this song the result of the utopian thoughts of a rockstar who was drowning in wealth, even though this song does have a radical meaning. Lyrics of the song *Imagine* Cloud Piece was inspired by the poem entitled Grapefruit by Yoko Ono. In this song Lennon consciously avoided slogan-like lyrics. Finally, Lennon chose to sing this song softly with ideas about a world without borders, a world without religion, a world where people can concentrate on the essential things about humanity in building society, rather than the fictions that often make life difficult. Lennon invites us to imagine that if religion, wealth and other things did not exist, the world would be a better place.

Album *Imagine* in 1971, became the theme song for the anti-war movement which wanted a peaceful world life. Visuals in the song video clip *Imagine*, the visual appearance is all white, namely wearing white clothes, a white piano, and an all-white room. This song became the theme song for the movement against the policy of war. "If one person dreams, then it remains a dream. "But if two people have the same dream, that's reality," said John. John's dream and also most people's dreams at that time were the same, namely *Love Peace No War*. *Imagine* was Lennon's most successful solo album in terms of sales (Hendi Triono, 2010:70-72).

Through the song *Imagine*, this legend from Liverpool, invites world citizens to imagine a life full of peace, no war, no one kills and no one dies, no poverty, everyone lives happily and peacefully (Hendi Triono, 2010: 129). In the movie *Imagine* (1988), Yoko Ono (John Lennon's wife) said, "*Imagine* is one facet of him, crystallizing his dreams for the world. Crystallized idealism, and that was something he really wanted to say to the world," said Yoko. In this statement it is clear that John Lennon through his song entitled *Imagine* voicing what he wants to say to the world with his phenomenal lyrics.

C. Construction of Song Meaning Imagine

1. Denotative Level

In terms of denotational meaning, overall it can be concluded that this song denotatively tells about John Lennon's anxiety about what was happening in the world at that time. Song *Imagine* released in 1971 at the same time as the conflict between Vietnam and America. Where the war was motivated by ideology, religion and territory. John Lennon in song *Imagine* invites everyone to imagine a world full of peace, without conflict, without religion, without

countries, without heaven and hell, without possessions, without greed, and without anyone feeling hungry.

a. First Verse

One of the research subjects, Nikolaus Heru S, said that the denotative meaning of this verse is to imagine that there is no heaven. As we know, some people in this world believe in the existence of heaven, there are also a few who don't believe in it. John Lennon continued that he said it would be easy if you tried. There is no hell beneath us. Above us there is only the sky. Like heaven, hell is also believed to exist by some people and quite a few people do not believe in its existence.

b. Second Verse

Based on the results of the interview, Nikolaus Heru as the research subject said that in this verse John Lennon invites you to imagine everyone living life today.

c. Third Verse

If seen in a denotative sense, based on the statement from Nikolaus above, this lyric is intended to convey that there are no countries. And it won't be difficult to do. John Lennon continued that no one should be killed or murdered over this. He also added, there is no religion either. As is the reality in most of the world, there are many conflicts that occur in this world due to territorial struggles and differences in ideology, including religion.

d. Fourth Verse

According to Riyadi Maskur, the subject of this research, he said that in this verse, imagine all the people in this world living a peaceful life without any conflicts occurring.

d. 5th Verse

Researchers studied the denotative meaning of this verse, the result of which was that John Lennon said that he was a dreamer and he was not the only one. He also invited everyone to join him and with that the whole world would unite. A similar statement was made by Nikolaus Heru as part of the research subject, he said that John Lennon was not the only dreamer and indirectly John Lennon invited everyone to join him.

e. 6th Verse

According to one of the subjects of this research, Nikolaus Heru, he said that in this verse there is an invitation to imagine if there were no possessions and John Lennon asked if it was possible to imagine it? He also continued that no one was hungry due to greedy people. And he said that all of them were brothers.

f. Seventh Verse

Nikolaus Heru, the subject of this research, said that in this verse there is the meaning of imagining all people throughout the world sharing with each other.

g. Eighth Verse

According to Nikolaus Heru as the research subject, in this verse John Lennon said that he was a dreamer and he was sure that he was not the only dreamer. He also hopes that everyone will join him for world unity.

There is a statement from Deri Fikri Fauzi, SS., M.Hum. As an expert to support the data triangulation stage. He believes that John Lennon composed the song *Imagine* by taking messages from an event. However, if you look at the current phenomenon, it will be more real if it turns out that a phenomenon that occurred in the past was used as an excuse by John Lennon to create it. These lyrics will last forever. He also said that he was a little pessimistic if the world would be like what John Lennon said in his song. Because if you look at it from a literary point of view, remembering that the richness of human imagination is incredibly unlimited. Imagining the conditions of a phenomenon based on this, would be another thing if we compared it with the conditions of the phenomenon in the field. Whether it's the opposite or hyperbole, the feeling is enhanced and will become more different, and that is called literature. He continued that we can spark our imagination so that apart from getting satisfaction or happiness, we also have other points of view that can enrich our insight.

2. Connotative Level

Connotatively, this song is John Lennon's dreams for the world. Several times he said *'imagine'* which means imagine. John Lennon wrapped his dreams and idealism into a song and a song was created *Imagine*. John Lennon wanted to live in a peaceful world without conflict due to differences such as differences in ideology, religion, ethnicity, nation, state, social class, and so on.

There was a statement made by one of the subjects of this research, namely Riyadi Maskur, who said that if you look at several verses, this song is utopian and is just a fantasy. Like imagine there is no heaven. Even though many religious people believe that heaven exists. Therefore, just imagine it. For

those who are not religious, perhaps this song represents their desires and what is in their hearts.

a. First Verse

From the results of an interview with a research subject named Nikolaus Heru, he said that connotatively it can be explained that John Lennon invited us to imagine that there is no place for good people or people who do good, namely heaven. Then he continued, there is no place for evil people or people who commit crimes, namely hell.

b. Second Verse

According to Nikolaus Heru, the connotative meaning of this verse is to imagine that everyone lives life only for today without thinking or worrying about what they will face or what will happen in tomorrow or the future. If viewed from a psychological and health perspective, these lyrics can be linked to the concept of Mindfulness.

c. Third Verse

In Nikolaus Heru's statement in this stanza there is the meaning of imagining that there will be no separation of territories. In reality there is regional separation. The separation of these regions was a result of the founding of a country. In this stanza there are lyrics "*And no religion too*" which means and also no religion. Based on the results of an interview with Nikolaus as part of the research subject, he said that the connotative meaning in the lyric fragment was that John Lennon imagined a life without religion. In the lyrics "*And no religion too*" According to researchers, it is clear that it is possible to imagine a life without religion. In this case, John Lennon expressed his concern about the existing reality, namely that there are many conflicts between humans that occur due to differences in religious beliefs.

d. Fourth Verse

This verse received support from one of the research subjects named Riyadi Maskur, he said that in the lyrics "*living life in peace*" Living in peace is everyone's dream and also the country's dream. Meanwhile, the connotative meaning in this passage based on the researcher's analysis is to imagine that everyone lives a peaceful life without any conflict. As previously written, John Lennon was a person who actively advocated for peace. Many of his actions were aimed at campaigning for peace. One of them is a

song *Imagine* this. There are jargons he uses like, “*give peace a chance*”, “*All you need is love*”, “*War is over! – If you want it*”.

e. 5th Verse

There was a statement from one of the sources named Nikolaus Heru S. According to Nikolaus, what John Lennon said was like inviting him into John Lennon's mind. Not to be open to events or happenings in the environment.

From the results of the researcher's analysis, this verse has a connotative meaning, namely that John Lennon wanted everyone to have the same vision or dream, namely the dreams he conveyed in the song *Imagine*. John Lennon believed that if all humans in this world had this dream, then there would be no conflict with each other and all humans in the world would be united without any things that divide one human being with another human being based on ethnic differences, race, class, nationality, and so on.

f. 6th Verse

Based on an interview statement from Nikolaus Heru, he is of the opinion that John Lennon really did not want any divisions based on class or group, including what he said in the verse above, namely life without ownership of property. In reality, in our environment there are terms like the rich and the poor. Apart from that, John Lennon touched on the realities of life around him. Where there are still many people who are hungry due to the greed of other humans. For this reason, John Lennon said in this verse that if there were no possessions or ownership of something, then he was sure that no one would be greedy and no one would be hungry. And he also said that all humans are brothers.

g. Seventh Verse

After the researcher examined this stanza, the researcher believes that in this stanza John Lennon invites people to imagine that everyone shares with each other and cares for each other. A similar thing was expressed by one of the subjects of this research, Riyadi Maskur. According to Riyadi, one sentence in this verse is enough to represent the entire content of the song, namely sharing the whole world and also equal rights. He also assumed that John Lennon also wanted to fight for the rights of the proletariat. Like the greed of bourgeois society. He continued that bourgeois society could share the world with proletarian society.

h. Eighth Verse

In this last stanza there are lyrics that were already in the previous stanza, namely the fifth stanza. According to Nikolaus Heru, the subject of this research, he said in this verse that what John Lennon said was like inviting him into John Lennon's mind. Not to be open to events or happenings in the environment.

3. Mythical Level

Analyzing the myth level, based on the results of an interview with one of the language experts, Deri Fikri Fauzi, he said that there was no myth or ideology to be conveyed in the song. He said that the song *Imagine* shows more self-internalization (*self internalization*). However, based on the results of the study or further thoughts from the researchers and from the results of interviews with the four research subjects, the song *Imagine* actually there are myths. Overall, there is an ideology that is very often mentioned by John Lennon, namely Peace. John Lennon imagined several things in these lyrics which aimed to achieve a life full of peace without conflict.

a. First verse

In this first stanza, according to researchers, John Lennon conveys the myth or ideology of his thoughts to imagine that there is no heaven or hell, because maybe it would be easier to live life. In these lyrics there are the words heaven and hell, which according to some people in the world believe in the existence of heaven and hell. One of the research subjects, Riyadi Maskur, also disputed the lyrics in this verse. In his interview he said that this song was utopian or imaginary. Like imagine there is no heaven. Even though many religious people believe in the existence of heaven.

b. Second Verse

There is a statement from one of the research subjects, Nikolaus Heru. He said in this verse there is a meaning to live life for today. Some people believe that there is something that must be prepared for provisions for the future, so many of them worry about what will happen in the future, which causes these people to enjoy life less. However, there are also some people who live life without worrying about what will happen tomorrow. They tend to enjoy each day more. In these lyrics, perhaps the ideology that John Lennon wanted to convey, more precisely, is living life for today without worrying about the future. This concept is called *Mindfulness*. According to Brown & Ryan, *mindfulness* is

a state with attention (*attention*) and awareness (*awareness*) on events in the present (Pranazabdian Waskito, 2019:116).

c. Third Verse

As we know, this earth consists of many countries, each of which has certain territorial boundaries between one country and another. This often triggers conflicts between one country and another, both in terms of territory and religion, which causes many victims as a result of these conflicts. As happened in the Vietnam war, which was caused by differences in ideology, religion, and even territorial struggles. Apart from that, there is a territorial conflict between Palestine and Israel which is still ongoing. There is a statement from one of the subjects of this research, Nikolaus Heru, who touched on this verse, he said that in this verse there is an ideology, namely peace, unity and equality. According to him, John Lennon invited everyone to imagine that there are no differences between one another, including differences in religion. So he invites everyone to imagine that there are no countries, including no religion. So that everyone lives in unity, peace, without any differences.

d) Fourth Verse

In this stanza there is an ideology to be conveyed, namely peace. Without conflict, war, or competition. Everyone lives life in true peace. And as said by one of the subjects of this research, Riyadi Maskur. He said that living life in peace is everyone's dream and the country's dream as well.

e) 5th Verse

According to one of the subjects of this research, Nikolaus Heru. He said that, in these lyrics, John Lennon conveys that perhaps in people's minds John Lennon was just a dreamer. John Lennon emphasized that he was not the only dreamer, he also invited people to join him in having the same dreams and he believed that everyone had dreams like those conveyed through songs. *Imagine* this then people all over the world will unite, together, and fight for the same thing. So, according to researchers, the ideology or myth in this stanza is unity. If everyone unites to have the same vision and dreams then everyone or the world will be united.

f) 6th Verse

Based on the results of an interview with one of the research subjects, Nikolaus Heru. He said that there is a sentence that states that imagine life without possessions. In

this life, there are many stigmas attached to society, one of which is that someone who has a lot of possessions is rich. Meanwhile, people who have little or no possessions are poor. John Lennon discusses this kind of stigma in this verse. Maybe with the absence of property or the stigma of 'the rich' and 'the poor' there would be no greedy people and no one would starve because everyone is a brother and sister and cares for each other. So the myth or ideology in this stanza is equality and togetherness.

g) Seventh Stanza

Based on a statement from a research subject named Nikolaus Heru S, he found that the myth or ideology contained in this verse is caring. In reality, there are still many people who don't care about the environment around them. This is in sharp contrast to the lyrics written by John Lennon in this verse. He wrote that imagine everyone sharing with each other and caring for each other, then there is no need for anyone to feel less or more.

h) Eighth Stanza

As discussed previously, in this verse John Lennon wrote that maybe in people's minds he was a dreamer. But he also emphasized that he was not the only dreamer. According to researchers in this verse, John Lennon invited people to join him in having the same dreams and he also believed that everyone had dreams as conveyed by him through songs. *Imagine* then everyone around the world will unite, be together, and fight for the same thing. There is a statement from one of the subjects of this research, Nikolaus Heru. He said that the ideology or myth in this verse is unity. Everyone is united to have the same vision and dreams. Dreams that make life better and more peaceful.

4. Social Criticism of Songs Imagine

There is a lot of social criticism in songs *Imagine*. This. Each verse has a social critique of social problems that occur around us, especially on this earth, one of which is that there are many conflicts that occur in the world so that this song as a whole conveys messages of peace.

a. First Verse

In the first stanza, according to Nikolaus Heru, the subject of this research, the existence of heaven and hell is necessary to remind someone to maintain their attitude. He took as an example the selfish high-ranking officials who did not see the

good and bad in what they did and did not care about the impact of what they did. He continued that if these high-ranking officials always remember and consider what impacts will occur, then they will consciously remember the existence of heaven and hell. So they think first before doing something.

Based on the results of the researcher's analysis, in this stanza it appears that there is a dream conveyed about people who believe in the existence of heaven and hell so that many people are competing to do good and not a few of them want to get *reward* from what he had done. In fact, to do good, we don't need to expect a reward, in other words, do good with sincerity.

b. Second Verse

In the second stanza, it seems to be confirmation of the first stanza. Which according to Nikolaus Heru as part of the subject of this research, he said that in this verse John Lennon said imagine everyone living life for today without worrying about what will happen in the future. To be precise, it's more about enjoying the moment at hand. As in the concept of mindfulness which was explained in the previous myth analysis section. If someone focuses on what they are facing in the present, then that person will be more grateful. With gratitude, of course it can make someone happier.

c. Third Verse

Based on the researcher's view, here John Lennon alludes to the reality that exists on earth where there are regions that are divided and produce countries.

As previously discussed, if you look at the year this song was released, at that time the Vietnam War was going on and there were many victims as a result of that war. Several factors caused the Vietnam War to occur due to differences in ideology, religion, territorial struggles and power. Meanwhile, according to one of the research subjects, Adhithan Hardiansyah. He doesn't agree with the lyrics "*Imagine there's no countries*" and "*And no religion too*" imagine there are no countries and no religions, no races, or that everything is the same. According to him, life cannot be like that because even though the aim is good for peace, according to him, every human being lives with their own thoughts and cannot live with the same thoughts or principles of life.

d. Fourth Verse

In the fourth stanza there is social criticism which according to researchers, this stanza touches on the many conflicts that occur between countries, tribes, races, religions, and so on. This conflict disrupts the continuity of life in this world, disturbing the peace of life with each other. In this verse John Lennon wrote the lyrics which mean "Imagine everyone living their life in peace".

According to Riyadi Maskur, the subject of this research, in his interview he said that peace is the ideal of every person and every country.

e. 5th Verse

In the fifth stanza in the researcher's study, there is social criticism which alludes to the fact that everyone has the same vision, namely the dream of living a better and more peaceful life. Without differences, the whole world will become one, not divided between one another, thus triggering conflict.

However, according to Adhithian Hardiansyah, the subject of this research, he believes that John Lennon forgot the true nature of humans who must socialize, have their own opinions and be a community of individuals. He also continued that each person is different and has their own opinions and characteristics. He also said that with these differences being able to understand each other also becomes a reference. He believes that if everyone were the same as what is in the song lyrics *Imagine* then the age will not progress and will not develop.

f. 6th Verse

In the sixth stanza, according to research by researchers, there is social criticism that touches on the bourgeoisie and the proletariat or the rich and the poor. Many people form a stigma that people who have a lot of wealth are rich or belong to the bourgeoisie, while people who have less are poor or belong to the proletariat. In this verse, according to researchers, John Lennon invites you to imagine that if there were no possessions in this world, there would be no greedy people and no one would be hungry. He also emphasized that all people are brothers, all people are equal, there are no caste or differences in position, and everyone has the same rights.

From the results of an interview with one of the subjects of this research, Muhammad Kahfi said that this song could

mean that people who are well off can share with each other, especially people who are less well off.

The subject of this research, Riyadi Maskur, also conveyed the same thing. He argued that in the lyrics "*no need for greed or hunger*" is a form of social criticism shown to corrupt people. He also continued that there is no need to be greedy because what is important is "*A brotherhood of man*" human brotherhood.

g. Seventh Verse

In the seventh stanza in the researcher's study, John Lennon invites us to imagine everyone sharing the world or what we could mean by sharing with each other. This stanza is like a confirmation of the social criticism contained in the previous stanza that there is no need for greedy people which results in many people feeling hungry. According to the researcher, the social criticism in this stanza is considering that there are many needy people who need help from well-off people. Based on the researcher's analysis, in this verse John Lennon said that imagine if everyone shared the world with each other, then everyone would have the same rights as creatures living in this world.

h. Eighth Verse

In the eighth stanza, this verse has the same lyrics as the fifth stanza. In the fifth and final stanza there is social criticism which according to researchers, this stanza alludes to the idea that everyone has the same vision, namely the dream of living a better and more peaceful life. Without differences, the whole world will become one, not divided between one another, thus triggering conflict.

Adhitian Hardiansyah as the subject of this research, he refutes these lyrics and he says that John Lennon forgot the true nature of humans who must socialize, have their own opinions, and be a community of individuals. He also continued that each person is different and has their own opinions and characteristics. He also said that with these differences being able to understand each other also becomes a reference. He believes that if everyone were the same as what is in the song lyrics *Imagine* Then the times will not progress and will not develop. However, Riyadi Maskur said something different. In his interview he argued that if we really have a high sense of humanity, a sense of belonging, then perhaps we will unite in having the same vision.

CONCLUSIONS

This song is John Lennon's concern about what was happening in the world at that time. Song *Imagine* released in 1971 at the same time as the conflict between Vietnam and America. In the denotative sense, it can be concluded that John Lennon invited everyone to imagine a world full of peace, without conflict, without religion, without countries, without heaven and hell, without possessions, without greed, and without who feel hungry.

For the connotative meaning, it can be concluded that this song is John Lennon's dreams for the world. Several times he said *'imagine'* which means imagine. John Lennon wrapped his dreams and idealism into a song and a song was created *Imagine*. On a mythical level, it can be concluded that there is an ideology that is very often mentioned by John Lennon, namely 'Peace'.

As for social criticism, there is a lot of social criticism in songs *Imagine*. This. Each stanza has a social critique of social problems that are happening around, especially on this earth. One of them is that there are many conflicts occurring in the world.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

In writing this article the researcher realizes that there are still many deficiencies in terms of language, writing, and form of presentation considering the limited knowledge and abilities of the researchers themselves. Therefore, for the perfection of the article, the researcher expects constructive criticism and suggestions from various parties.

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